

AUTOMORPHISMS AND 2-LOCAL AUTOMORPHISM OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL JORDAN ALGEBRAS

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In 1997, P. Semrl introduced and investigated so-called 2-local derivations and 2-local automorphisms on operator algebras. He described such maps on the algebra $B(H)$ of all bounded linear operators on an infinite-dimensional separable Hilbert space H . Namely, he proved that every 2-local derivation (automorphism) on $B(H)$ is a derivation (respectively an automorphism).

A similar description of 2-local derivations for the finite-dimensional case appeared later in the work of S. Kim and J. Kim. In the paper of Y. Lin and T. Wong 2-local derivations have been described on matrix algebras over finite-dimensional division rings. Sh. Ayupov and K. Kudaybergenov suggested a new technique and have generalized the above-mentioned results mentioned above for arbitrary Hilbert spaces. Namely, they proved that every 2-local derivation on the algebra $B(H)$ of all linear bounded operators on an arbitrary Hilbert space H is a derivation. A similar result is obtained for automorphisms by them. Sh. Ayupov, K. Kudaybergenov and F. Arzikulov extended the above results for 2-local derivations and gave a proof of the theorem for arbitrary von Neumann algebras.

M.J. Burgos, F.J. Fernandez Polo, J.J. Garces and A.M. Peralta established that every 2-local $*$ -homomorphism from a von Neumann algebra into a C^* -algebra is a linear $*$ -homomorphism. These authors also proved that every 2-local Jordan $*$ -homomorphism from a JBW^* -algebra into a JB^* -algebra is a Jordan $*$ -homomorphism. Later, Sh. Ayupov and K. Kudaybergenov prove that any 2-local automorphism on an arbitrary AW^* -algebra without finite type I direct summands is an automorphism.

Sh. Ayupov and K. Kudaybergenov also proved that every 2-local automorphism on a finite-dimensional semi-simple Lie algebra over an algebraically closed field of characteristic zero is an automorphism and showed that each finite-

dimensional nilpotent Lie algebra with dimension ≥ 2 admits a 2-local automorphism which is not an automorphism.

The present paper is devoted to automorphisms and 2-local automorphisms on Jordan algebras.

Sh. Ayupov, F. Arzikulov, N. Umrzaqov and O. Nuriddinov proved that every 2-local 1-automorphism (i.e. implemented by single symmetries) on a finite-dimensional semi-simple Jordan algebra over an algebraically closed field of characteristics different from 2 is an automorphism.

In the present paper, we investigate 2-local automorphisms on low-dimensional Jordan algebras. Namely, we describe automorphisms and 2-local automorphisms on three-dimensional T_9 Jordan algebra .

Let T_9 be a Jordan algebra with the following table multiplication

$$e_1^2 = e_1 \quad n_1^2 = n_2 \quad n_2^2 = 0 \quad e_1 n_1 = \frac{1}{2} n_1 \quad e_1 n_2 = n_2 \quad n_1 n_2 = 0$$

i.e., three-dimensional spin factor.

Theorem 1.1. A linear operator φ on T_9 is an automorphism if and only if the matrix generating φ is equal to one of the following matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & 0 \\ -a_{21}^2 & -a_{21}a_{22} & a_{22}^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Theorem 1.2. Every local automorphism on T_9 is an automorphism.

Theorem 1.3. Every 2-local automorphism on T_9 is an automorphism.

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